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The Duration of Civil Proceedings in the Italian Regions

It decreased on average by 10.98% between 2012 and 2019

Istat-BES calculates the duration of civil proceedings in the Italian regions. The data refer to the actual average duration in days of the proceedings defined in the ordinary courts. The data is produced by the Ministry of Justice, Department of Judicial Organization, Personnel and Services-General Directorate of Statistics and Organizational Analysis. The data refer to the period 2012-2019.

Ranking of the regions by value of the duration of civil proceedings in the Italian regions in 2019. Basilicata is in first place for the duration of civil proceedings in 2019 with a value of 760 days, followed by Calabria with a duration of 755 days, and by Puglia with a value of 637 days. In the middle of the table are Molise with a value of 422 days, Tuscany with a value of 375 days, and Abruzzo with a value of 341 days. Friuli-Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a value of 193 days, Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 171 days and Valle d'Aosta with a value of 136 days. In 2019 the average value of the duration of civil proceedings was equal to a value of 398 days in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the regions by percentage change in the duration of civil proceedings between 2012 and 2019. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first place value of the percentage change in the duration of civil proceedings between 2012 and 2019 with a value equal to 13.25 % equal to a variation of 20 units, followed in second place with a value of 6.39% equal to a variation of 29 units, followed by Lombardy with a variation of 4.47% equal to a variation of 11 units. In the middle of the table there are Piedmont with a variation equal to -4.41% equal to a variation of 9 units, followed by Tuscany with a variation of -4.82% equal to a variation of -19 units, followed by Sardinia with a variation of -5.2% equal to a variation of -27 units.

North. The number of days of duration of civil proceedings in Northern Italy increased between 2012 and 2019 from an amount of 272 days up to a value of 257 days or equal to a reduction of 15 days equal to a value of -5.51 %. Between 2012 and 2013 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Northern Italy decreased from an amount of 272 days to a value of 262 days or a reduction of 10 days equal to a variation of -3.68%. Between 2013 and 2014 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Northern Italy increased from an amount of 262 to a value of 271 days or a variation of 9 days equal to an amount of 3.44%. Between 2014 and 2015 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Northern Italy increased from an amount of 271 to a value of 283 days or equal to a variation of 12 days equal to an amount of 4.43%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of civil proceedings in Northern Italy increased from an amount of 271 days to a value of 283 days or equal to a variation of 12 units equal to an amount of 4.43%. Between 2015 and 2016, the value of the duration of civil proceedings decreased from an amount of 283 days to a value of 269 days or equal to a variation of -

14.00 days equal to -4.95%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the duration of the civil proceedings decreased from an amount of 269 days to a value of 263 days or equal to a variation of -6.00 units equal to an amount of -2.23%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Northern Italy increased from an amount of 263 days to a value of 270 days or equal to a variation of 7 units equal to a value of 2.66%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Northern Italy decreased from an amount of 270 days to a value of 257 days equal to an amount of -13.00 days equal to -4.81%.

Center. The duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy increased from an amount of 422 in 2012 to an amount of 404 in 2019 or a change equal to an amount of -18 days equal to an amount of -4.27%. Between 2012 and 2013 the duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy decreased from an amount of 422 days to a value of 412 days or equal to a variation of -10.00 days equal to an amount of -2.37% . Between 2013 and 2014 the duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy increased from an amount of 412.00 days up to a value of 413 days or equal to a variation of 19.00 days equal to an amount of 4.61% . Between 2014 and 2015 the duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy increased from an amount of 431.00 days up to a value of 436 days or equal to a variation of 5.00 days equal to an amount of 1.16% . Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the duration of civil proceedings decreased from an amount of 436 days to a value of 424 days or equal to a variation of -12.00 days equivalent to an amount of -2.75%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy decreased from an amount of 424 days to a value of 411 days or equal to a value of -13.00 days equal to a variation of -3, 07%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy decreased from an amount of 411.00 days to a value of 407 days or equal to a variation of -4.00 units equal to a value of - 0.97%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Central Italy decreased from an amount of 407 days to a value of 404 days or equal to a variation of -3.00 days equal to an amount of -0, 74%.

South.The value of the duration of civil proceedings in Southern Italy decreased from an amount equal to 697 days in 2012 to a value of 583 days in 2019 or a reduction of -114 days equal to an amount of -16.36%. Between 2012 and 2013 the duration of civil proceedings in the South increased from a value of 697 days up to a value of 704 days or equal to a variation of 7 days equal to an amount of 1.00%. Between 2013 and 2014 the duration of civil proceedings in the South increased from an amount of 704 days up to a value of 756.00 days or equal to a variation of 52 days equal to an amount of 7.39%. Between 2014 and 2015 the duration of civil proceedings in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 765 days to a value of 733 days or equal to a variation of -23.00 units equal to a variation of -3.04%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 733 days to a value of 696 days or a reduction of -37 days equal to an amount of -5.05%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the duration of civil proceedings in Southern Italy decreased from a value of 696 days to a value of 632 days or equal to a value of -64 days equal to a variation of -9.20%. Between 2017 and 2018 the duration of civil proceedings in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 632 days to a value of 592 days or equal to an amount of -40.00 days equal to an amount of -6.33 units. Between 2018 and 2019 the duration of civil proceedings in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 592 days to a value of 583 days or equal to a value of -9.00 days equal to a variation of -1.52%.

Correlation matrix. Through the analysis of the correlation matrix of the values of the duration of the days of civil proceedings it is possible to verify that in general the Italian regions have a degree of positive correlation. However, there are exceptions. The ordering of the Italian regions that have a degree of negative correlation with other regions is therefore shown below, namely:

- Trentino-Alto Adige: shows a degree of negative correlation with Emilia-Romagna -0.8, Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of -0.79, Abruzzo with a value of -0.67, Lazio with a value of -0.54, Puglia with a value of -0.49, Campania with a value of -0.327, Basilicata with a value of -0.27, Sardinia with a value of -0.23, Marche with a value of -0.1781, Sicily with a value of -0.06, and Tuscany with an amount of -0.0495 units;
- Lombardy: shows a degree of negative correlation with Emilia-Romagna -0.5653, Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of -0.5242, Puglia with a value of -0.50, Abruzzo with a value of -0.48 units, Lazio with a value of -0.44, Basilicata with an amount of -0.3334, Campania with a variation of -0.3316, Sicily with a variation of -0.1891, and Sardinia with a value of -0.0304.
- Liguria: has a negative correlation with Trentino-Alto Adige with a correlation coefficient value equal to -0.583, Calabria with a correlation coefficient variation equal to -0.39, Veneto with a correlation coefficient variation equal to -0.30, Umbria with a change in the correlation coefficient equal to -0.19, and Molise with a correlation coefficient value equal to -0.14;
- Piedmont: is negatively correlated with Liguria with a correlation coefficient value equal to -0.102 units, with Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a correlation coefficient value equal to an amount of -0.1631, with Emilia-Romagna with a correlation coefficient value equal to -0.1578, and from Lazio with a correlation coefficient value equal to -0.1746;
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia: has a negative correlation with Umbria with a correlation coefficient value of -0.38, with Molise with a correlation coefficient value equal to -0.3257, and with Calabria with a correlation coefficient value equal to an amount of -0.4099;
- Valle d'Aosta: has a negative correlation with Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of -0.583, and with Umbria with a correlation coefficient value of -0.1206;
- Emilia-Romagna: has a negative correlation with Molise with a correlation coefficient value of -0.0601, and with Calabria with an amount of -0.3944 units;
- Lazio: has a negative correlation with Molise with an amount equal to -0.1698 and with Calabria with an amount of -0.2522 units;
- Tuscany: has a negative correlation with Lazio with an amount equal to -0.0204 units.

The analysis of the correlation matrix highlights that the regions that have the most negative correlation with other regions in terms of the length of days of civil proceedings are also the regions that have a shorter trial duration. In fact, while the average duration of civil proceedings in general for the Italian regions in 2019 was equal to a value of 398.1 days, the duration of civil proceedings in the regions with negative correlations is equal to 254 days, i.e. they are more efficient. by 35% with a reduction of the days of civil proceedings equal to an amount of 143.21 days.

Conclusions. The duration of civil proceedings in the Italian regions decreased on average by an amount of -49.10 units or by a value of -10.98% between 2012 and 2019. However, significant differences persist between the North, the Center, and the South of Italy. In the North, the duration of civil proceedings in 2019 was equal to a value of 257 days, in the Center equal to a value of 404 days and in the South equal to 583 days. A civil proceeding in Central Italy lasts about 147 days longer than in the North, with a 57.19% increase in duration. A civil proceeding in the South lasts 326 days longer than in the North or an increase of 126.85%.

Duration of civil judicial proceedings 2019		
Rank	Region	2019
1	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 760
2	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 755
3	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 627
4	<i>Campania</i>	★ 567
5	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 567
6	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 492
7	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 483
8	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 423
9	<i>Molise</i>	★ 422
10	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 375
11	<i>Abruzzo</i>	☆ 341
12	<i>Veneto</i>	☆ 328
13	<i>Marche</i>	☆ 326
14	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	☆ 300
15	<i>Lombardia</i>	☆ 257
16	<i>Liguria</i>	☆ 244
17	<i>Piemonte</i>	☆ 195
18	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	☆ 193
19	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	☆ 171
20	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	☆ 136
	<i>Mean</i>	★ 398,1

Duration of civil judicial proceedings 2019

